

Studies on *bis* N-phenylhydroxamic Acids as Metal Complexing Ligands Part III : Glutaryl, and Pimelyl-*bis*-N-phenylhydroxamic Acids

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Glutaryl-*bis*-N-phenylhydroxamic acid (R_gH_2) and pimelyl-*bis*-N-phenylhydroxamic acid (R_pH_2) form complex compounds with Cu(II), Fe(III), Al(III), V(V) and U(VI). The compounds isolated are $Cu(R_gH)(OH)$; $Fe_2R_g(R_gH)_2(OH)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$; $Al_2R_g(R_gH)_2(OH)_2 \cdot 5H_2O$; $VO_2(R_gH)_2 \cdot 3H_2O$; $UO_2R_g \cdot 3H_2O$; and CuR_p ; $Fe_2R_p(R_pH)_2(OH)_2(OH_2)_2 \cdot 2.5H_2O$; $Al_2R_p(R_pH)_2(OH)_2(OH_2)_2 \cdot 3H_2O$; $[VO(OH)]_3(R_p)_2(OH)_2$; $UO_2(R_pH)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$; $(UO_2)_2R_p(R_pH)_2$.

Fe(III), Al(III) and U(VI) compound of R_gH_2 lose 1, 5 and 3 molecules of water, while Fe(III) and Al(III) compounds of R_pH_2 lose 2.5 and 3 molecules of water respectively on heating to constant weights at 110°.

That the succinyl-*bis*-N-phenylhydroxamic acid¹ forms chain-type compounds but the adipyl-*bis*-N-phenylhydroxamic acid², having two more carbon atoms in the chain between the two hydroxamic acid residues may act as tetradentate ligand has brought in much interest regarding the studies of such reagents. Therefore to study the chelating properties of glutaryl-*bis*-N-phenylhydroxamic acid (R_gH_2), and pimelyl-*bis*-N-phenylhydroxamic acid (R_pH_2) they have been isolated. They are found to form complexes with Cu(II), Fe(III), Al(III), V(V) and U(VI). The complexes with R_gH_2 appear to be predominantly of chain-type.

The magnetic properties of some of the complex compounds have been studied. They are high-spin complexes.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of R_gH_2 and R_pH_2 : The compounds were prepared by the condensation of respective acid-chlorides (1 mole) with slight excess of recrystallized phenyl-hydroxylamine (2.1 moles) in ice-cold ether solution containing 2 moles of dry pyridine, following the method employed by Lukaschewitsch³ and Lutwick and Ryan⁴, in the preparation of some N-acyl phenyl hydroxylamines.

1. N. N. Ghosh and D. K. Sarkar, *Jour. Indian Chem Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 550.
2. N. N. Ghosh and D. K. Sarkar, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 528.

Purification processes :

(a) The pimelyl-*bis*-N-phenylhydroxamic acid was purified through the formation and decomposition of its copper complex.

The precipitated reagent was filtered, washed with hot water, and dissolved in a dilute solution of ammonia. On acidification of the ammonia extract with dil. H_2SO_4 (final $\text{pH} = 2$) white crystalline precipitate appeared. It was filtered, washed with water and dried in air.

(b) The crude glutaryl-*bis*-N-phenylhydroxamic acid was directly dissolved in dil. ammonium hydroxide and the pure compound R_gH_2 was isolated on acidification with dil. H_2SO_4 as usual. The product was further purified by recrystallization from large volume of aqueous ethanol.

Both the reagents are insoluble in benzene, petroleum ether, sparingly soluble in ether, soluble in ethanol and dilute ammonium hydroxide solution.

The results of analyses and melting points are shown in Table-I.

TABLE I

Compounds	m.p.	% of Carbon		% of Hydrogen		% of Nitrogen	
		Found	Required	Found	Required	Found	Required
R_gH_2	147°	65.32	64.97	5.69	5.73	9.02	8.92
R_pH_2	131°	65.98	66.67	6.45	6.43	7.72	8.18

Preparation of the metal-chelates

1. *Copper (II) chelates* : To excess of aqueous ethanolic solutions of copper acetate (1.1 mole) dilute aqueous ethanolic solutions of the reagents (1 mole) were added with stirring. With R_gH_2 a greenish yellow precipitate appeared in cold at $\text{pH} \approx 4.0$, but in the formation of the copper compound with R_pH_2 warming of the resultant solution at $\text{pH} \approx 3.5$ to 60° for 10 mins. was required.

The pH was adjusted by adding dilute solution of sodium acetate. The precipitates were filtered, washed with warm water, aqueous ethanol, and air-dried. The compounds are insoluble in water and sparingly soluble in aqueous ethanol.

The copper complex of R_gH_2 was heated at 110° for 2 hrs. but showed no loss in weight.

2. *Iron (III) chelates* : Dilute solution of FeCl_3 (1 mole) was dropwise added to equal volumes of ethanolic solutions of R_gH_2 and R_pH_2 (2 moles), which developed red colour. By mixing few drops of dilute ammonia the pH s were adjusted to ≈ 2 and ≈ 1.5 respectively.

Isolation of the complex of R_gH_2 : A red precipitate appeared (at $\text{pH} = 2$), which was filtered and subsequently washed several times with boiling 1 : 1 acetone-ethanol mixture.

3. W. O. Lukaschewitsch, *Ann.*, 1936, **521**, 198.

4. G. D. Lutwick and D. E. Ryan, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1954, **32**, 949-955.

Table II

Compounds with compositions	Colour	m.p.	% of Nitrogen		% Metal	% of loss on heating at 110°		No of moles of H ₂ O lost on heating at 110°	Temp. in °K
			Found	Reqd.		Found	Reqd.		
1. Cu(R _p H)(OH)	Greenish-yellow	—	4.0	7.07	7.12	16.13	16.15	—	No Loss — 1.91 305
2. Fe ₂ R _p (R _p H) ₂ (OH) ₂ , H ₂ O	Red	205°	2.0	7.67	7.63	10.36	10.14	1	1.65 1.63 5.97 303
3. Al ₂ R _p (R _p H) ₂ (OH) ₂ , 5H ₂ O	White	—	3.5	7.52	7.53	4.70	4.84	5	8.10 8.07 — —
4. VO ₂ (R _p H), 3H ₂ O	Red	—	1.5	6.03	6.23	11.39	11.32	—	— — Dia. 301
5. UO ₂ R _p , 3H ₂ O	Reddish-brown	—	4.5	4.37	4.41	37.84	37.42	3	8.40 8.49 — —
6. CuR _p	Yellowish-green	203°d	3.5	15.66	15.76	6.73	6.95	—	— — 1.87 301
7. Fe ₂ R _p (R _p H)(OH) ₂ (OH) ₂ , 2.5H ₂ O	Magenta-red	190°e	1.5	6.94	6.73	8.94	8.94	2.5	3.64 3.60 5.95 302
8. Al ₂ R _p (R _p H) ₂ (OH) ₂ (OH) ₂ , 3H ₂ O	White	—	3.5	7.03	7.00	4.39	4.50	3	4.55 4.50 — —
9. Al ₂ R _p (R _p H) ₂ (OH) ₂ (OH) ₂ (anhydrous)	White	—	—	7.30	7.34	—	—	—	— — — —
10. [VO(OH)] ₂ (R _p H)(OH) ₂	Chocolate	—	1.5	5.74	5.80	15.62	15.83	—	— — Dia. 301
11. UO ₂ (R _p H) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	light brown	95°d	3.0-3.5	5.59	5.67	24.23	24.08	—	— — — —
12. (UO ₂) ₂ R _p (R _p H) ₂	Reddish-brown	—	3.5	5.40	5.38	30.31	30.46	—	— — — —

The red compound was dried in air. It is sparingly soluble in acetone, ethanol and water, m.p. = 205°.

Isolation of the complex of R_gH_2 : Excess of R_pH_2 which appeared first was filtered off. The solution on keeping deposited shining magenta-red crystals. They were filtered, washed with (1 : 1) aqueous-ethanol and air-dried.

The compound is slightly soluble in ethanol, but insoluble in water. It melts with decomposition at 190°.

The Fe(III) complexes of R_gH_2 and R_pH_2 on heating at 110° to constant weights lost in weight without showing any change in colour, and the losses correspond to 1 and 2.5 molecules of water respectively.

The melting points of the compounds do not change on dehydration.

3. *Aluminium (III) chelates*: Aqueous ethanolic solutions of aluminium nitrate (1 mole) were mixed with equal volumes of aqueous ethanolic solutions of the reagents (1.6 moles) with stirring. The pHs were adjusted to 3.5 by adding requisite amounts of dilute sodium acetate solution. The crops of precipitates were filtered off. Latter crops of white sponzy precipitates, which appeared were separated from the mother liquor by decanting off the clear liquid, and then washed thoroughly by trituration with excess of 1 : 2 aqueous-ethanol. They were finally recrystallized from ethanol, filtered, and air-dried. They are soluble in ethanol, insoluble in water, and have high melting points.

The Al(III) complexes of R_gH_2 and R_pH_2 on heating at 110° to constant weights lost in weights. Losses correspond to 5 and 3 molecules of water respectively.

4. *Vandium (V) chelates*: Dilute solutions of the respective reagents (1 mole) in acetone were mixed with dilute solutions of potassium metavanadate (1.2 moles) with stirring when yellow colour developed in each case. Total volume was made to 250 ml by diluting with required amount of (1 : 3) aqueous-ethanol. By adding a few drops of dil. HCl the pHs were adjusted to 1.5; chocolate precipitate appeared. They were warmed at 60° for 10 mins, allowed to cool and settle, filtered, washed with (1 : 2) aqueous-ethanol. The precipitates were dissolved in hot (1 : 1) acetone-ethanol mixture — R_gH_2 and R_pH_2 complexes formed cherry-red and violet solutions which on gradual evaporation deposited water-insoluble shining cherry-red and chocolate crystals respectively. They were filtered, washed with aqueous-ethanol and air-dried.

Both the complexes are diamagnetic and decompose on warming and slowly on keeping.

5. *Uranium (VI) chelates*: With R_pH_2 two different compounds were isolated, having the composition U(VI) : R_pH_2 = 2 : 3 and 1 : 2.

(a) To excess of uranyl acetate (1.1 mole) solutions in aqueous-ethanol, ethanolic solutions of the reagents, R_gH_2 and R_pH_2 (1 mole) were added dropwise with stirring. pHs were adjusted to 4.5 and 3.5 respectively by adding dilute sodium acetate solution, when roddish brown precipitates appeared. They were filtered, washed with (1 : 1) aqueous-ethanol, water and air-dried. R_gH_2 and R_pH_2 form 1 : 1 and 2 : 3 compounds respectively. Both are sparingly soluble in aqueous-ethanol and insoluble in water.

On heating the compound of R_pH_2 at 110° to constant weight for 2 hrs the reddish brown colour changes to brown and loses 3 molecules of water.

(b) The second compound of R_pH_3 formed on gradual addition of an (1 : 1) aqueous ethanolic solution of uranyl acetate (1 mole) to ethanolic solution of excess of reagent (2.2 moles). When the pH was carefully adjusted to 3.0-3.5 with sodium acetate solution brown pasty precipitate appeared. It was separated from supernatant mother liquor, and washed with very dilute aqueous-ethanol by decantation. The precipitate was finally washed with water and air dried. It is highly soluble in acetone and rectified spirit, and melts with decomposition at 95° . Compositions of the complexes, and results of analyses, and magnetic data of some of the complexes are shown in Table II.

Nitrogen in these compounds were determined by modified Kjeldahl's method⁵, and the μ_{effs} were calculated by using Pascal's constants⁶.

Further work with such reagents is in progress in this laboratory. Thanks are due to Dr. T. N. Chakravorty for some micro-analyses.

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5. T. S. Ma, R. E. Lang and J. D. McKinley, *Mikro. Chimica Acta*, 1957, 368.
6. P. W. Selwood, '*Magnetochemistry*', Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, 1955, p. 92.